

ANTIOXIDANT AND HYPOGLYCEMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LACTOBACTERIA

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Abstract. *Intestinal microbiota and excessive accumulation of polysaccharides and a decrease in body's immune system are important in the occurrence of symptoms of hyperglycemia. The lactobacteria strains are included into the group of beneficial bacteria of the intestinal microbiota and have an effective effect in reducing the complications that occur in diabetes. Antioxidant and hypoglycemic activity were investigated in the study of 37 lactobacteria isolates. α -amylase enzyme activity was effectively stopped by 4 lactobacteria (*L. plantarum* TK1, *L. plantarum* KA3, *A. kunkeei* 1 and *E. faecium* 1) isolates. The lactobacteria isolates have been recommended for use as antidiabetic probiotics.*

Keywords: *intestinal microbiota, lactobacteria, antioxidant, diabetes mellitus, glucose, and α -amylase*

Introduction

The world is paying attention to reducing the risk of diabetes, providing affordable, high-quality treatment and care for patients. Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by persistent hyperglycemia caused by decreased insulin production or impaired insulin activity. Although many drugs have been developed to regulate the production and use of insulin, stop the production and absorption of glucose, block the reabsorption of glucose in the urine, and normalize glucose levels, these drugs have side effects. This can cause a number of diseases. Intestinal microbiota and excessive accumulation of polysaccharides and a decrease in body's immune system are important in the occurrence of symptoms of hyperglycemia. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* KLDS1.0901, *L. paracasei*, *L. rhamnosus* NCDC 17 and *L. rhamnosus* GG, *L. salivarius* AP 32, *L. reuteri* GL-104 and *L. plantarum* HAC01 LAB strains improve antioxidant activity and intestinal permeability.

Studies have shown that LAB strains inhibit the activity of α -amylase and α -glucosidase enzymes. It has effectiveness in glucose tolerance, blood glucose levels, total cholesterol and low-density lipoproteins [Amirsaidova D.I. 2021 p 445-457]. Creating a biological drug with antioxidant and hypoglycemic properties that does not have side effects on the organism is relevant today.

Research goal. Determination antioxidant and hypoglycemic activity of local lactobacilli strains.

Materials and methods.

Medicinal plants from *Taraxacum officinale*, *Heliánthus tuberósus*, *Ajuga turkestanica* and different sources isolated 37 LAB isolates were used in the study. LAB isolates are stored at -800C in the laboratory collection "Microbiology and Biotechnology of Probiotics" of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Antioxidant activity of the isolates DFGP radicals [Li K.T.2005, p 388-391] and hydroxyl radicals [Wang H. 2022 p 1363] based on partial modification of the recommended methods,

superoxide anion radical inhibitory activity was investigated using the spectrophotometric method [Wu D., 2014. r.- 14]

The α -amylase inhibitory activity of the samples was determined by A.M. Ugoleva to the method. It was performed on the basis of homogenates of the pancreas and small intestine accordingly. The amount of protein in tissues was determined with the Lowry method [Ugolev A.M. 1969. c 187-192].

Results and discussion.

When studying the antioxidant activity (AF) of SAB isolates *L. plantarum Mal1*, *Enterococcus faecium 1*, *L. plantarum TK1*, *L. plantarum KA3*, *Apilactobacillus kunkeei 1*, *E. faecium f1*, and *L. plantarum TK2* have high antioxidant activity (table 1).

Table 1

Antioxidant activity of *Lactobacillus* isolates

№	Strains	Antioxidant index (%)					
		DFPG inhibition of the free oxygen radical		Inhibition of superoxide anions		Inhibition of hydroxyl radical	
		Supernatant	Intact	Supernatant	Intact	Supernatant	Intact
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	Control (vitamin C)	99		91,37		88,21	
1	<i>L. plantarum Mal 1</i>	80	93	70,2	85	80,2	74
2	<i>L. plantarum Kp5</i>	87,5	0	75,4	72,8	18,0	78,5
3	<i>E. faecium 1</i>	84	86,7	74,0	82	77,9	54,8
4	<i>E. faecium R1</i>	84,5	12	68,4	90	48,2	80,73
5	<i>L. plantarum TK1</i>	77	85	80,5	77,6	76,8	70
6	<i>L. plantarum KA3</i>	62	87	82,4	76,4	77,7	72
7	<i>E. faecium R3</i>	91	83	76,4	83,47	56,68	60
8	<i>L. plantarum K2</i>	75	86	72	77,4	67,9	71,4
9	<i>L.delbrueckii R2</i>	71	73	69,8	84,8	74,5	74
10	<i>L. rhamnosus 925</i>	90	71	76,9	80,7	80,3	57
11	<i>E. faecium R2</i>	90	0	80,5	86	56,7	81,7
12	<i>E. durans</i>	88	62	75,2	80	76,18	72
13	<i>E.faecium F2</i>	89,5	19	72,7	84,2	35,5	79,8
14	<i>L. plantarum Kp1</i>	82,3	0	67,5	88,3	30,2	81,2
15	<i>L. plantarum Kp2</i>	71,4	16	65,5	78,5	32,0	79,6
16	<i>L.plantarum Kp3</i>	62,4	0	68,0	70,6	12	80,4
17	<i>A. kunkeei1</i>	82	64	86,4	75	80	78
18	<i>P. acidilactici B</i>	89,9	8,4	63,2	84,6	22,4	78,5
19	<i>P. acidilactici S</i>	83,6	0	86,5	75,68	10,6	75,2

20	<i>L. plantarum R1</i>	75	0	68,4	74,36	45,7	68,9
21	<i>L. plantarum R2</i>	67,54	48,83	89,9	70,23	40,2	56,0
22	<i>L. plantarum R3</i>	64,24	52,68	74,23	75,9	38,5	64,2
23	<i>L. plantarum R4</i>	68,33	48,10	72,29	77,9	36,2	36,5
24	<i>L. lactis R1</i>	76,22	46,27	72,99	74,31	15,6	56,2
25	<i>L. lactis R2</i>	63,5	50,06	72,33	76,58	14,8	48,7
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
26	<i>E. hirae R3</i>	70,29	48,34	68,49	75,39	12,2	68,4
27	<i>E. faecalis R3</i>	68,4	55,29	73,12	75,72	56,6	78,6
28	<i>L. mesenteroides</i>	75,42	51,29	74,19	70,47	38,9	45,8
29	<i>L. sakei R1</i>	66,5	52,26	72,68	77,66	40,2	47,2
30	<i>W. sibirica R1</i>	65,28	51,46	75,3	77,25	57,8	50,6
31	<i>P. pentosaceus R1</i>	74,0	0	0	72,25	45,0	56,9
32	<i>E. faecalis Sh</i>	56,4	48,6	75,2	78,2	40,2	56,4
33	<i>L. plantarum Av</i>	54,2	48,7	68,9	68,5	38,5	72,7
34	<i>L. debrueckii D</i>	42,6	49,9	65,2	77,2	54,0	63,2
35	<i>E. faecium f1</i>	68,4	78,6	56,4	70,4	56,2	65,5
36	<i>L. rhamnosus 2</i>	56,8	58,4	52,68	75,7	45,6	56,4
37	<i>L. plantarum TK2</i>	60,4	53,4	55,6	54,4	59,8	55,4

The antioxidant activity of the supernatant and whole cells of these isolates was 55-93%.

The inhibitory effect of α -amylase enzyme activity was studied with lyophilized cells and their culture fluid (CF) of isolates (table 2).

Table 2

α -amylase inhibitory activity of *Lactobacillus* isolates

№	Strains	Inhibition of α -amylase enzyme activity, (%)	
		lyophilized cells	culture fluid
1	Control	100	
2	<i>L. plantarum TK1</i>	33.33	83,3
3	<i>L. plantarum KA 3</i>	38.61	84,3
4	<i>L. plantarum Mal</i>	11,34	83,8
5	<i>L. kunkeei1</i>	38,5	83,8
6	<i>E. faecium1</i>	35,75	82,9
9	<i>E. faecium R3</i>	18,30	80,3
10	<i>L. plantarum TK2</i>	25.08	81,8

The inhibitory activity in CF did not differ between isolates (80%), this is inhibitory effect was noted that it was 2-2.5 times higher than in cells by the lyophilic method. α -amylase inhibitory activity differed among isolates. *L. plantarum TK1*, *L. plantarum KA3*, *A. kunkeei 1* and *E. faecium 1* isolate have the most effective activity, i.e equal to 33.33%, 38.61%, 38.5% and 35.75%

Summary. *Lactobacillus* isolates inhibited from 55% to 93% of free radicals the activity. The inhibition activity of α -amylase enzyme of LAB isolates was determined from 80 to 84% in their culture fluid and from 33.33 to 38.61% in lyophilized cells.

REFERENCES

1. Amirsaidova D.I., Bekmurodova G.A., Miralimova Sh. M., Imamaliev B.A. The Hypoglycemic Activity of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated From Medicinal Plants Of Uzbekistan And Their Probiotic Potential Journal of Pharmaceutcal research international 33(60B): 2021. 445-457, 22
2. Lee K.T. Wang H, Chung M.Y., Cho D.H., Park C.S. Resistance of *Lactobacillus casei* KCTC 3260 to Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS): Role for a Metal Ion Chelating Effect. // Journal of Food Science. 2005; 70(8): p 388-391.
3. Wang H., L. Li. Comprehensive Evaluation of Probiotic Property, Hypoglycemic Ability and Antioxidant Activity of Lactic Acid Bacteria. // *Foods*. 2022; 11(9):p-1363
4. Wu D., M. Z. Sun, C. Zhang, Y. Xin. Antioxidant Properties Of Lactobacillus And Its Protecting Effects To Oxidative Stress Caco-2 Cells. // *J Anim Plant Sci* 2014. 24(6): p.14.
5. Уголев А.М..Определение амилалитичкой активности // Исследование пишиваретельного аппарата у человека–Л.: Наука, 1969. с 187–192.
6. Zaripova M., Vypova N., Bekmurodova G.A., Amirsaidova D., Aripov T., Gayibov U., Miralimova S., Gayibova S. The hypoglycemic potential of endophytic *Lactobacillus kunkeei*, isolated from Dandelion flowers in rats. *Journal of Basic and Applied Pharmacology* Vol. 2 No.1 January - June 2022. p. 043-51.